

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding Psychological Dependence on Internet and Social Networking among Degree Students in Selected College at Hassan

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Abstract:

Background of the study: Today's children and young people have grown up in a world that is very different from that of most adults. Nearly half the world's population- more than 3 billion people-are under the age of 25. Eighty-five per cent of youth live in developing countries and India has the largest population of adolescents in the world being home to 243 million individuals aged 10-19 years. Within the world of the young, adolescents are at a particularly formative stage. These 1.2 billion adolescents between the ages of 10 and 19 are brimming with energy and possibilities. Their minds are open to acquiring knowledge, learning skills and absorbing values.

METHODOLOGY: The research design is the plan, structure and strategy of investigation for answering the research questions. It is the overall plan or blue print the researcher selects to carry out the study. The research design selected for the present study is Pre-Experimental Design (i.e, one group pre-test and post-test pre experimental design). In this design pre-test is conducted followed by video assisted teaching programme and then post-test for the same group after 7 days. This study was conducted in Government Degree College at Hassan. Data were analyzed in terms of objectives of the study.

FINDINGS: Result indicates that majority of the degree students lacked knowledge on psychological dependence on internet and social networking. The Video Assisted Teaching Programme given by the investigator helped the degree students to improve their knowledge. The effectiveness of VAT was tested in terms of gain in knowledge and the findings showed that it was statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study proved VAT is an effective strategy in improving the knowledge compared to their pre-test knowledge scores.

CONCLUSION: The finding of the study concluded that the degree students have lack of knowledge on psychological problem due to internet and social networking. The implementation of VAT interventions which will help them to create awareness and helps to develop positive attitude towards psychological dependence on internet and social networking.

Keywords:- Internet, social networking, psychological dependence effectiveness of VAT and clinical variables and Socio-demographic variables.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is health that is real wealth and not piece of gold and silver."

- Mahatma Gandhi

The one thing that has had the greatest impact on the lives of the people in modern times is computer. Over the past twenty years, computers have gone from being monstrous curiosities taking up the entire space in large rooms, to relatively small boxes on almost every desk.¹

Youth is the part of life that succeeds from childhood, the period of existence preceding maturity or age; the whole early part of life, from childhood to manhood. The youth is a condition or quality of being young. An early period of development or existence. It is the time of life between childhood and maturity.²

Today's children and young people have grown up in a world that is very different from that of most adults. Nearly half the world's population- more than 3 billion people-are under the age of 25. Eighty-five per cent of youth live in developing countries and India has the largest population of adolescents in the world being home to 243 million individuals aged 10-19 years. Within the world of the young, adolescents are at a particularly formative stage. These 1.2 billion adolescents between the ages of 10 and 19 are brimming with energy and possibilities. Their minds are open to acquiring knowledge, learning skills and absorbing values.²

Advanced technology has made the world more connected than ever through social media that can be accessed from seemingly everywhere. Some of the most knowledgeable users of this technology are our youth. Adolescents throughout the country regularly use the internet, cell phones, and video games to gather information and communicate with each other. This ability to interact with others is the unique feature of social media which provides powerful new ways for adolescents to create and navigate their social environments.³

Over years, the prices of computers have drastically slashed down: not only for computers but also in the field of smartphones segment. Every month new models of smart phones with advanced feature are released in to the market companies are on competition in cutting down the prices of these phones. Therefore almost every adolescents are having smartphones: therefore there is easy access of internet and social networking.

The mass appeal of social networks on the Internet could potentially be a cause for concern, particularly when attending to the gradually increasing amounts of time people spend online.³

On the Internet, people engage in a variety of activities some of which may be potentially to be addictive. Rather than becoming addicted to the medium *per se*, some users may develop an addiction to specific activities they carry out online.⁴

There is a great variety of content that can be accessed on the Internet.the content can be about something useful or something harmful.⁵

The content that learners search from downloadable cell phone ring tones to social networking web sites. Some content may not be safe for learners to view for instance having access to information. Internet is important because it has the power to influence the learners knowledge and decision.⁶

In real sense Smartphone is a mobile phone with advanced features and functionality beyond traditional functionalities like making phone calls and sending text messages. The Smartphone are equipped with the capabilities to display photos, play games, play videos, navigation, built-in camera, audio/video playback and recording, send/receive e-mail, built in apps for social web sites and surf the Web, wireless Internet and much more. Due to same reasons the Smartphone's now become a common choice for consumers along with the use in business as it was initially intended for business users only.⁸

Today in modern trend there is widely using variety of internet and social network applications like Googleplus and facebook etc by the young generation.

A study reveled that Prolonged use of social networking sites (SNS), such as Facebook, may be related to signs and symptoms of depression. In addition, SNS activities might be associated with low self-esteem, especially in children and adolescents.¹⁰

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Study Design and Participants

Present study was a pre- experimental one group pretest posttest design without control group.

A Simple random sampling technique was used to select the 30 subjects for the present study. Degree students who were able to understand, read and write Kannada or English and available at the time of data collection are selected for the study.

In this study research design is the plan, structure and strategy of investigation for answering the research questions. It is the overall plan or blue print the researcher selects to carry out the study. In this design pre-test is conducted followed by video assisted teaching programme and then post-test for the same group after 7 days. This study was conducted in Government Degree College at Hassan. The sample for the study comprised of 30 students of Government Degree College at Hassan. Purposive sampling technique was used to draw the samples, which is the type of non-probability sampling technique.

III. INSTRUMENTS

A. Socio-demographic Variables and Clinical characteristics

Socio demographic data consists of 16 items related to demographic data of the subjects such as age, gender, type of family, place of residence, religion, family income, type of college, class which studying, education of father, occupation of parents and using internet and social networking, previous information, place of access, money spending per day, purpose of using, hours spending daily on internet and social networking.

Structured knowledge questionnaire regarding psychological dependence on internet and social networking among degree students. It consists of 39 items.

B. Data Collection Procedures

Prior permission was taken from relevant institutions before the beginning of data collection procedure. The study participants were identified during the study period at Govt degree college, Hassan. Every students was fulfilled the inclusion criteria was approached for data collection. Consent was obtained by the interviewers before participants underwent the structured interview which lasted approximately 20 to 30 minutes. All the information collected was based on student's self report. Pre-test conducted to assess the Psychological dependence on internet and social networking followed by administration of Interventions by VAT Method. On 7th day post test conducted.

C. Data Analysis

Frequency and percentage distribution will be used to analyze demographic data of degree students, Mean, percentage and standard deviation will be used to assess the level of knowledge of degree students. Paired 't' test will be used to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programmed. Chi square test will be used to find association

between post test knowledge score and demographic variables.

IV. RESULTS

The collected data was analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics. The overall pre-test mean knowledge score was 56.6% followed by post-test 96.7% with mean enhancement of knowledge score of 23.4% which is statistically significant. The paired ‘t’ test was computed and it was 24.16 which is higher than the table value and is significant at 5% level of significance .Video assisted teaching programme was effective in increase in knowledge.

There was a significant difference between mean pre-test and post-test knowledge score. Calculated χ^2 value revealed significant association between demographic variables like Age, Gender, religion, family income, education level of the father, place of residence, purpose of using internet, hour spending per day on internet and social networking, place of access of internet and money spending per day of respondents with their post test knowledge scores

Description of Assessment of pre-test knowledge level on psychological dependence on internet and social networking.

A. Analysis of pre-test knowledge scores

Knowledge Level	Category	Respondents	
		Number	Percent
Inadequate	≤ 50 % Score	6	20.0
Moderate	51-75 % Score	8	26.6
Adequate	> 75 % Score	16	53.3
Total		30	100.0

Table 1: Classification of Respondents on Pre-test Knowledge level on Psychological dependence on Internet and Social networking

Table 1 show the classification of respondent’s knowledge according to their knowledge level in the pre-test. The data showed that, majority of the respondent

(53.3%) had adequate knowledge, 26.6% had moderate knowledge and 20% of them had the adequate knowledge.

N=30

No.	Knowledge Aspects	Statements	Max. Score	Respondents Knowledge			
				Mean	SD	Mean (%)	SD (%)
I	General information	8	8	5.5	1.6	68.75	20
II	Causes	4	4	2.06	1.22	51.5	30.5
III	Signs and symptoms	8	8	4.3	2.22	53.7	27.7
IV	Advantage & disadvantage	4	4	2.2	1.6	55.0	40
V	Diagnosis	6	6	3.13	1.28	52.6	21.3
VI	Prevention	9	9	4.6	2.07	51.1	23
	Combined	39	40	22.03	6.2	56.4	15.89

Table 2: Aspect wise pre-test knowledge scores of respondents on Psychological dependence on Internet and Social networking

Table:2 shows that the aspect wise mean and mean percentage of pre-test knowledge scores of respondents in different aspects of knowledge questionnaire mainly the mean percentage of pre-test score of respondents for the whole test is 56.4%. The highest mean percentage (68.75%) of knowledge scores of respondents is obtained in the aspect general information on psychological dependence on

internet and social networking. It is followed by 55.0% advantages and disadvantages of internet and social networking aspect; 53.7% in the signs and symptoms of psychological dependence on internet and social networking, 51.1% in causes and prevention of psychological dependence on internet and social networking aspect.

B. Analysis over all aspect wise Post test Knowledge Scores

N=30

Knowledge Level	Category	Respondents	
		Number	Percent
Inadequate	≤ 50 % Score	0	0.0
Moderate	51-75 % Score	12	40.0
Adequate	> 75 % Score	18	60.0
Total		30	100.0

Table 3: Classification of Respondents on Post test Knowledge level on Psychological dependence on Internet and Social net working.

Table 3 shows the classification of respondent’s knowledge according to their knowledge level in the post-test. The data showed that, majority of the respondent’s

(73.3%) had adequate knowledge, 26.7% had Moderate knowledge and none of them had the inadequate knowledge.

N=30

No	Knowledge Aspects	Statements	Max. Score	Respondents Knowledge			
				Mean	SD	Mean (%)	SD (%)
I	General information	8	8	6.16	0.96	77.0	20
II	Causes	4	4	3.06	3.00	76.5	75
III	Signs and symptoms	8	8	6.13	0.60	76.6	7.5
IV	Advantage & disadvantage	4	4	3.23	1.82	80.7	45.5
V	Diagnosis	6	6	4.5	0.03	70.0	0.5
VI	Prevention	9	9	6.76	0.84	75.1	9.3
	Combined	39	39	29.03	5.7	74.4	14.6

Table 4: Aspect wise Post-test Knowledge scores of respondents on Psychological dependence on Internet and Social networking

Table-4 shows that the aspect wise mean and mean percentage of pre-test knowledge scores of respondents in different aspects of knowledge questionnaire mainly the mean percentage of post-test score of respondents for the whole test is 74.4. The highest mean percentage (80.7%) of knowledge scores of respondents is obtained in the aspect of

advantages and disadvantages. It is followed by 77.0% in general information of psychological dependence on internet and social networking aspect; 76.0% in causes and signs and symptoms aspect. 75.0% in prevention aspect.

C. Effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge scores of whole test.

N=30

Aspects	Max. Score	Respondents Knowledge				Paired ‘t’ Test
		Mean	SD	Mean (%)	SD (%)	
Pre test	39	22.03	5.7	56.6	15.5	76.4*
Post test	39	29.03	6.2	96.7	14.6	
Enhancement	39	7.03	5.70	23.4	17.9	

Table 5: Over all Pre test and Post test, mean, SD, mean%, SD% Knowledge scores on psychological dependence on Internet and social networking

* Significant at 5% level,

$$t(0.05,29\ 29(df) = 2.05$$

Table.5 Depicts the overall pre-test mean percentage of knowledge score of respondents on psychological dependence on Internet and Social networking was 40.0% and post-test mean was 83.6% with an enhancement 42.8%. To test the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programe paired ‘t’ test was computed. The calculated paired ‘t’ test value of (t =32.82*) is greater than the table value at 0.05 level of significance which indicate that there is a

significancant diffrence between pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of whole test of respondents. Hence the null hypothesis H_{01} was rejected and research hypothesis H_{11} is accepted. It was concluded that the Video Assisted Teaching Programme was effective in increasing knowledge of Degree respondents regarding psychological dependence on Internet and Social networking.

N=30

Knowledge Level	Category	Classification of Respondents				χ^2 Value
		Pre test		Post test		
		Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
Inadequate	≤ 50 % Score	6	20.0	0	0.0	24.16*
Moderate	51-75 % Score	8	26.6	12	40.0	
Adequate	> 75 % Score	16	53.3	18	60.0	
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0	

* Table 6: Comparison of pretest and post test Knowledge level of respondents.

Significant at 5% level,

$$\chi^2(0.05, 2df) = 5.99$$

The Table.6 Shows that in pre-test 76.7% of respondents have inadequate knowledge, 23.3% had moderate knowledge and none had adequate knowledge. The post-test revealed majority of the respondent 73.3% had adequate knowledge, 26.7% had Moderate knowledge and

none of them had the inadequate knowledge. The calculated chi square value ($\chi^2=24.16^*$) was more than table value and significant at 5% level. which suggestive of significant difference between pre –test and post-test knowledge level of respondents.

D. Effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on aspect wise knowledge score

N = 30

No.	Knowledge Aspects	Respondents Knowledge (%)						Paired 't' Test
		Pre test		Post test		Enhancement		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
I	General information	5.5	1.6	6.16	0.96	1.3	1.22	5.90*
II	Causes	2.06	1.22	3.06	3.00	1.3	0.73	10*
III	Signs and symptoms	4.3	2.22	6.13	0.60	2.2	2.0	7.5*
IV	Advantage & disadvantage	2.2	1.6	3.23	1.82	1.2	0.911	7.05*
V	Diagnosis	3.13	1.28	4.5	0.03	1.3	1.20	4.9*
VI	Prevention	4.6	2.07	6.76	0.84	3.6	2.77	7.05*
	Combined	22.03	6.2	29.03	5.7	8.1	7.0	76.4*

Table 7: Aspect wise Pre- test and Post- test knowledge score on psychological dependence on internet and social networking and calculated paired 't' test value.

* Significant at 5% level,

$t(0.05, 29df) = 2.05$

Table 7 reveals that, in the aspect of "general information" the mean pre test knowledge score was 5.5 ± 1.6 and post-test knowledge score was 6.16 ± 0.96 with enhancement of 1.3 ± 1.22 ($t_{29} = 5.90$) at 0.05 level of significance. In the aspect of "causes" the mean pre test knowledge score was 2.06 ± 1.22 and post-test knowledge score was 3.06 ± 3.00 with enhancement of 1.3 ± 0.73 ($t_{29} = 10$) at 0.05 level. In the aspect of "signs and symptoms" the mean pre test knowledge score was 4.3 ± 2.22 and post-test knowledge score was 6.13 ± 0.60 with enhancement of 2.2 ± 2.0 ($t_{29} = 7.5$) at 0.05 level. In the aspect of "advantages and disadvantages" the mean pre test knowledge score was 2.2 ± 1.6 and post-test knowledge score was 3.23 ± 1.82 with enhancement of 1.2 ± 0.911 ($t_{29} = 7.05$) at 0.05 level. In the aspect of "diagnosis" the mean pre test knowledge score was 3.13 ± 1.28 and post-test knowledge score was 4.5 ± 0.03

with enhancement of 1.3 ± 1.20 ($t_{29} = 4.9$) at 0.05 level. In the aspect of "prevention" the mean pre test knowledge score was 4.6 ± 2.07 and post-test knowledge score was 6.76 ± 0.84 with enhancement of 3.6 ± 2.77 ($t_{29} = 7.05$) at 0.05 level of significance. The calculated paired 't' test values based on pre-test post-test knowledge scores of all the aspects were more than the table value at 0.05 level of significance with 29 degrees of freedom. It indicates that mean differences between mean pre-test and post-test knowledge scores are significant at 0.05 level of significance for all the aspects. There is significant difference between mean pre-test and post-test knowledge scores regarding. Hence null hypothesis H_{01} was rejected and research hypothesis H_1 was accepted for all aspects of knowledge.

Demographic variables	Category	Sample	Knowledge level				χ^2 Value	P value
			moderate		Adequate			
		N=30	N	%	N	%		
Age group (years)	16-20	12	5	41.6	7	58.3	5.37*	P<0.05
	21-23	28	3	10.7	15	53.5		
Gender	Male	15	3	11.5	12	80.0	3.94*	P<0.05
	Female	15	5	33.3	10	66.6		
Religion	Hindu	20	05	25	15	75	3.73*	P<0.05
	Christian	05	1	20	2	40		
	Muslim	05	4	80	3	60		
Type of family	Nuclear	25	7	3.8	18	96.1	1.79 NS	P>0.05
	Joint	5	1	25	4	75		
Family income/month	5000 /Less than 5000	20	3	15	17	85	7.02*	P<0.05
	Rs 10,000 -1 lac	10	5	50	5	50		
Educational level of Father/Guardian	No formal Education	16	5	31.2	11	68.7	28.2*	P<0.05
	Primary education High school	4	2	50	2	50		
	Graduation and above	10	01	10	9	90		
Occupation of Father/Guardian	Agriculture	8	2	25	6	75	2.8 NS	P<0.05
	Government employee	9	4	44.4	5	55.5		5
	Private employee	10	1	10	9	90		P>0.05
	Self employed/business	3	1	33.3	2	66.6		
Place of residence	Urban	21	7	33.3	14	66.6	16.5*	P<0.05
	Rural	9	01	11.1	8	88.8		

Table 8: Association between Demographic variables and Post test Knowledge level on Psychological dependence on Internet and Social networking

Significant at 5% Level,

NS: Non-significant

Table: 8 revealed that the calculated χ^2 values with regard to age ($\chi^2 = 5.3(S), P < 0.05$); (Figure.22), Gender ($\chi^2 = 3.94, P < 0.05$) (Figure.23), religion ($\chi^2 = 3.37, p < 0.05$), figure 24; purpose of using internet ($\chi^2 = 7.10; p < 0.05$) figure 25; hour spending on online per day ($\chi^2 = 8.1; p < 0.05$) figure 26; money spending per day to use internet and social networking ($\chi^2 = 3.7; p < 0.05$) figure 27, monthly family income ($\chi^2 = 7.02, P > 0.05$) were more than the table values at 0.05 level of significance, which shows significant association between the post-test and demographic variables. Hence the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected and research hypothesis H_{12} is accepted with regard to above mentioned demographic variables. The calculated χ^2 values with demographic variables like type of family and occupation of the father were less than the table values at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted and research hypothesis H_{12} is rejected.

V. DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the discussion of major findings and recommendations in accordance with the objectives of the study and the hypotheses. The problem stated is "a study to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding psychological dependence on internet and social networking among degree respondents in selected college at Hassan".

Researchers have studied Internet and social networking use and psychological dependence and the number of references in the available literature. This study bridges these gaps by developing a consensus definition of psychological dependence and its diagnostic

criteria finally, this study elicited and incorporated opinions from the respondents on methods and strategies to minimise the negative effects of psychological dependence.

In the present study the frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variables of participants revealed that most of the respondents (60%) were in the age groups of 20-21 years, most of the respondents (83.3%) were from nuclear family, majority of the respondents (70%) were from urban area, majority respondents (33.3%) occupation of head of the family is in private company, majority of respondents (53.3%) father's education is graduation and above, Most of the respondents (66.6%) were from the family income of Rs5000 to 10,000/-.100% of the respondents having previous knowledge regarding Internet and social networking.

A. *First objective of the study: To determine the knowledge of psychological dependence on internet and social networking among degree students.*

The present study showed that degree students had inadequate knowledge regarding psychological dependence on internet and social networking with the mean knowledge score percentage 41.8%. This finding of the study is supported by study to investigate the awareness of internet addiction among 143 university students which revealed that only 44% of respondents were aware of internet addiction.¹⁵

The findings are also consistent with the study conducted by China Internet Network Information Center to find out the knowledge and attitude on impacts of social networking among 100 randomly selected high school

students which showed them more than 62% of participants had not having adequate knowledge.²¹

B. Second objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted programme by comparing pre- test and post - test scores

The present study revealed that, the mean percentage pre-test knowledge scores is 42.5%; and post-test knowledge score is 86.3%. The comparison between the pre-test and post-test knowledge scores showed that the pre-test knowledge level of 76.7% of respondents regarding psychological dependence on Internet and Socialnetworking was inadequate that of remaining 23.3% was moderate; whereas the post-test level of knowledge of 73.3% of respondent was adequate and 28% of them were moderate.²²

These results are consistent with the findings of a study conducted by Barker V, to evaluate the attitude, perceived awareness levels on internet addiction knowledge before and after pre-test among 51 among junior high school students which showed that provision of a 1-hour training class did result in significant improvement in attitude, perceived awareness and knowledge regarding internet.

These findings are also supported by the results of study conducted by Bonds-Raacke to improve the knowledge regarding and disadvantages advantages of internet among the youth aged between 14 to 17 years . The study results showed that there was a significant difference between the pre-test ($m=9.36$, $s=3.91$) and the post test mean ($m=15.99$, $s=3.09$) scores. Paired “t” test, ($t_{29} = 11.466$) at 5% level of significance.⁴⁷

These results can also be compared with results of an study conducted on impact of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge and attitude regarding ergonomics to prevent health hazards of extended computer usage among computer science and engineering students at selected college, Hassan by R .Raghunandan H.S in the pre-test to prevent health hazards of extended computer usage among computer science and engineering students, were found to be poor knowledge in pretest ($m=9.36$, $sd=3.91$) and while in the post test mean ($m=15.99$, $sd=3.09$) score, there was significant improvement in the level of knowledge($p<0.01$).⁴⁸

C. Third objective: To find the association between knowledge of psychological dependence on intern at and social networking:

In the present study the calculated X2value for age, gender, religion, family income, educational level of the father, place of residence, purpose of using internet, money spending daily for internet and social networking using, place of access of internet, hours spending to use internet and social networking per day were more than the table value and calculated X2were less than the table value for all other demographic variables. Therefore it was concluded that there was a significant association between post test knowledge level respondents and their age, gender, religion, family income, educational level of the father, place of residence purpose of using internet, money spending daily for internet and social networking using, place of access of

internet, hours spending to use internet and social networking per day.

These results can also be compared with results findings of the respondent, a survey was conducted among 211 pre university students in Jordan to investigate.

pre university student's knowledge regarding internet addiction . It was found that there were no significant differences between pre university student's gender and educational level and e total knowledge score.²⁴

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The study was helpful to find the effectiveness of intervention VAT on selected psychological dependence on internet and social networking among degree students at govt degree college , Hassan and suggests that psychosocial intervention focusing to reduce the selected psychological problems of degree students would contribute to the improvement of their quality of life. Future researches can investigate the effect of various psychological measures to reduce the psychological problems with the aim of improving their overall quality of life. Hence more study can be conducted by using different interventional methods to achieve optimal reduction in psychological dependence and improvement in quality of life.

- **Limitations:** Although present study has able to explain that VAT interventions are effective on psychological problems of degree students. Sample size was limited to 30 degree students.
- **Ethical Clearance:** Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethical committee of Govt degree college , Hassan
- **Source of funding:** Self
- **Conflict of Interest:** Nil

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations are stated;

- A similar study can be undertaken with a large sample including from different sections of society to generalize the findings.
- A study can be conducted to find out the prevalence rate using of internet and social networking and related health problems and its implementation on students life.
- A study can be carried out to evaluate the efficiency of various interventional methods like yoga, deep breathing exercises, etc.

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